

Australia

Austria

Azerbaijan

Bahamas

Bahrain

Bangladesh

Barbados

Belarus

Botswana

Brazil

British Virgin Islands

Brunei Darussalam

Bulgaria

Burkina Faso

Burundi

Cambodia

Colombia

Comoros

Congo

Cook Islands

Democratic Republic of the Congo

Denmark

Djibouti

Dominica

Equatorial Guinea

Eritrea

Estonia

Ethiopia PDR

Ethiopia

Faroe Islands

Fiji

Finland

France

French Guiana

French Polynesia

Gabon

Gambia

Georgia

Germany

Ghana

Greece

Grenada

Guadeloupe

Guam

Haiti

Honduras

Hungary

Iceland

India

Indonesia

Iran (Islamic Republic of)

Iraq

Ireland

Israel

Italy

Jamaica

Kiribati

Kuwait

Kyrgyzstan

Lao Peoples Democratic Republic

Latvia

Lebanon

Lesotho

Liberia

Libya

Liechtenstein

Lithuania

Luxembourg

Mauritania

Mauritius

Mexico

Micronesia (Federated States of)

Mozambique

Myanmar

Namibia

Nauru

Nepal

Netherlands

New Caledonia

New Zealand

Norway

Occupied Palestinian Territory

Oman

Pacific Islands Trust Territory

Pakistan

Panama

Papua New Guinea

Paraguay

Peru

Philippines

Poland

Portugal

Puerto Rico

Qatar

Republic of Korea

Republic of Moldova

Saint Helena

Saint Kitts and Nevis

Saint Lucia

Saint Pierre and Miquelon

Saint Vincent and the Grenadines

Samoa

Sao Tome and Principe

Saudi Arabia

Senegal

Serbia and Montenegro

Serbia

Seychelles

Sierra Leone

Singapore

Slovakia

Slovenia

Solomon Islands

Somalia

South Africa

Spain

Sri Lanka

Sudan (former)

Suriname

Swaziland

Sweden

Switzerland

Syrian Arab Republic

Tajikistan

Thailand

The former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia

Timor-Leste

Togo

Tokelau

Tonga

Trinidad and Tobago

Tunisia

Turkey

Turkmenistan

Tuvalu

Uganda

United States of America

United States Virgin Islands

Uruguay

USSR

Uzbekistan

Vanuatu

Venezuela (Bolivarian Republic of)

Viet Nam

Wallis and Futuna Islands

Western Sahara

Yemen

Yugoslav SFR

